

PRINCIPLES OF FINANCIAL INNOVATION

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Abstract: *This article discusses the process of changing the financial system under the influence of innovative processes and the development of banking institutions in this context. The principles of financial innovation are indicated, the options for differentiating financial services are presented, and an example of the classification of innovative financial products according to the field of application is given.*

Keywords: *innovation, financial institutions, banks and non-banking organizations, innovative financial products, FinTech.*

The spread of the digitization process is accompanied by the penetration of innovations into all sectors of the economy. The financial market is no exception, and here financial innovations are manifested by strengthening the influence of information technology on decision-making at all stages of the activity of financial market entities, from the formation of a financial institution, from the search for a counterparty to the conclusion of a deal and further cooperation. Indeed, an important part of financial relations is moving to the digital space, now it is being formed within the concept of the "Internet of Things" (IoT, "Internet of Things").

Digitization is a general characteristic of modern financial innovations and is associated with the increasing influence of information and communication technologies in the process of production and provision of financial services. Objectively, its impact is the increasing impact of information technology on human life in general, the information of the population and the increase in the number of Internet users (from 2000 to 2019, the average growth rate of the share of active users of the world's population is -13, 44%) taking into account. In 2018, total global

investment in financial technology was approximately \$111.8 billion, almost doubling from the previous year.

The development of financial technologies is accompanied by a change in the activity models of organizations that provide financial services: if earlier it was mainly banking organizations, now the initiative is taken by FinTech companies, which are able to provide similar services more effectively as non-banking organizations. are getting Contributes to the regulatory, gradual and mediating effect of this trend, but new products. The FinTech industry tends to be less adjustable and flexible than the banking industry, which increases systemic risks. Here, old approaches to macro-regulation are of little use, and new solutions are needed for protocol certification, registry requirements, and what open interfaces can look like. At the same time, classic banks are not lagging behind in development either: protecting their position, they absorb technological development mechanisms based on existing systems, including non-bank organizations.

Digitization processes are translations, and they can be expressed as the following stages of development.

The first stage coincided with the activation of the change of financial technologies, the development of new financial instruments, primarily derivatives, and led to a significant restructuring of the entire world financial system.

The second stage is characterized by the introduction of mobile banking, mobile payments and social networks into banking: in this case, the interaction of customers with banks has actually changed.

The third phase has occurred in recent years and is associated with the increasing popularity of technologies that allow non-bank organizations to provide banking services. These changes are an important challenge for banks, which have prompted them to enter a sharp competition where cheap financial resources and access to customers are not the key to ultimate success, but require radical changes in business approaches.

Currently, the main trends in the global financial ecosystem market are consolidation of assets and expansion of transactions, global expansion of FinTech

infrastructures, in particular in the areas of payment infrastructure, actively increasing investments in distributed ledger technologies, in particular blockchain; Intensification of trends in the insurtech industry, digital expansion of banking services, integration of innovative enterprises with banking services, transformation of classic, traditional sectors with financial services taking into account new features, increasing regulatory requirements for companies operating in this sector. New technological systems are implemented based on the following principles:

- availability and speed of work (the Internet as the main place for providing services);
- scalability and openness (Open-Api interfaces);
- distribution feature (distributed registry technologies);
- safety and security of customer data (authentication, encryption and cryptography technologies);
- standardization (tokenization of contract elements), cloud storage for data storage, analysis - use of large volumes of data and machine learning methods.

The implementation of these principles allows unregulated participants to provide services independently of banks, which creates the basis for increased competition.

When distinguishing the solutions offered by the FinTech industry today, it is necessary to distinguish the classification directions [4]: solutions for banking and non-banking organizations according to the field of activity; based on the technologies used (distributed registers, cloud services, big data); analysis by current activity directions data, customer engagement, risk management. If we consider the issue of changing the provided financial services, it should be noted that their spectrum has increased significantly. In particular, the FinTech segment includes:

- * products related to making payments - mobile payments, e-commerce, P2P transfers, alternative means of payment; block technologies, in particular, cryptocurrencies, stand out;
- * financing tools that provide an alternative to banking institutions from the point of view of lending - from the point of view of crowdfunding, landing, factoring and

investment business - asset management tools - private finance management, Robo-trading, risk management;

* technologies mediating in the provision of financial services - database tools, markets;

Services related to regulating the RegTech (regulatory technologies) industry are focused on ensuring compliance with regulatory requirements and suptech (supervisory technologies) that help regulators perform their oversight functions.

In conclusion, it can be noted that digitalization of financial relations is an integral part of changing not only financial markets, but also the economy as a whole. Services resulting from the integration of innovative technologies and financial services are platform oriented. In this context, it is necessary to standardize the methods of accessing information and ensure security, and develop technologies to protect against new risks.

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